

WAVETABLE-INSPIRED ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK SYNTHESIS

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ABSTRACT

We present WTIANNS, a method of database-driven sound synthesis with significant resemblance to wavetable synthesis. The primary difference between the technique presented and standard wavetable synthesis is that our method uses a multilayer perceptron (MLP) to generate wavetables in realtime. The MLP provides a continuous mapping from a set of psychoacoustic timbral features of an analyzed single-cycle waveform segment to the harmonic amplitudes of that waveform segment. In particular, we use either Bark spectrum or Bark Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (BFCCs) as input parameters. The results of the mapping are highly dependent on the character and timbral variance of the analyzed sound.

Two significant advantages of our method over wavetable synthesis include its accommodation of higher dimensionality and the fact that the waveforms are automatically derived from a pre-existing recording. WTIANNS is not intended to *emulate* the recording it is based on, but to generate waveforms that are related—whether by interpolation or extrapolation—to those of the recording. This method encourages sound designers to explore the timbre space of recordings in a manner that is divorced from time.

1. WAVETABLE-INSPIRED ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK SYNTHESIS

The method described here, denoted WTIANNS¹, involves three phases: (1) offline timbral analysis, (2) offline ANN training, and (3) realtime sound synthesis. In order to perform an accurate analysis for WTIANNS, we assume that the analyzed sound is periodic and monophonic.

1.1 Offline Timbral Analysis

The first phase is a conversion of a time-series waveform into metadata-tagged frames that describe multidimensional timbral characteristics, plus pitch, inharmonicity, and loudness. One may ask why pitch and loudness should be extracted, since the aim is to create a continuous *timbre* space, and timbre is separate from these features. The reason is that timbres of varying pitch or loudness are not directly comparable; timbres can only be compared given a constant pitch and loudness.

Rather than use a pitch detection algorithm for this work, we used recordings that are already tagged with pitch. The file names include the pitch class and octave, which is then converted to a fundamental frequency f_0 in hertz via string mapping. We do, however, detect approximate loudness via Stevens' power law [1].

The timbral features used to control the synthesized waveforms currently include the Bark Spectrum and the Bark-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (BFCCs). [2]. The Bark spectrum provides a psychoacoustically-distributed description of spectral energy. The BFCCs express the patterns in a Bark spectrum via discrete cosine transform (DCT). The first BFCC describes overall energy, so it is not useful for timbre description; thus we discard it. The next BFCC estimates brightness, as it shows the weighting of the spectrum towards lower or higher frequencies. The following BFCC is a measurement of extremity in the low and high frequencies relative to mid-range frequencies. The BFCCs become less intuitive beyond this, but follow a pattern of fitting varying wavelength cosines to the Bark-distributed spectrum. We experiment with several truncations of the Barks/BFCCs as input parameters for resynthesis, using 3, 5, or 20 coefficients.

After tagging the frames with these features, each frame is resampled so that one wavelength is exactly represented within the frame. This step is crucial to making WTIANNS 'wavetable-inspired': in wavetable synthesis, each waveform is generally given the same number of samples, and the current time sample is an interpolation function of a phase increment dependent on frequency.

Each of the resampled waveforms is transformed into the frequency domain via Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). The DC component, along with the bins above Nyquist are discarded. We keep the magnitude spectrum and discard phase. This ensures that crossfading between waveforms causes no phase cancellation, and simplifies the training process if phase can be ignored.

The f_0 , loudness, inharmonicity, and Barks/BFCCs will be used as inputs to a multilayer perceptron, and the modified spectrum will be used as the outputs. Before training the network, we perform several preprocessing steps.

For the first step, a ceiling is placed on the high harmonics for prevention of noise in training and of aliasing in resynthesis. During the resampling of each single-cycle waveform, the interpolation scheme may add artifacts—partials exceeding the frequency at which Nyquist was remapped to. These upper harmonics, though low in am-

¹ Code and samples of WTIANNS available at <https://nvssynthesis.github.io/wtianns.html>

plitude, would decrease the accuracy of training. Also, if the observation is resynthesized at its original frequency, these additional partials would exceed Nyquist. Thus, we null out bins above this frequency.

Next, any observations that fall outside of a dynamic range are discarded from the set. This range is based on an optional high and low percentile of the loudnesses. This ensures that we do not train the ANN on noisy data considered to be silence or any loud ‘microphone bumps’ that may have corrupted the observation set. For the work presented, we omit observations with loudness less than the 10th percentile of the set.

The following step is based on the fact that we hear amplitudes on a nonlinear scale. Thus, the ANN should ideally have a matching error measure. For this, we raise each bin to the power of 0.3, which approximates sones as long as the amplitude exceeds 40 dB SPL [2].

Another step taken is a truncation of the output spectrum. Regardless of the analysis window size, once these frames have been resampled, the majority of the bins beyond some high frequency should be close to zero. It will be inefficient to train the neural network on this information, and likewise inefficient to calculate all of these outputs in realtime synthesis. Thus, we truncate the spectra to a number of bins on the order of 40. This may be adjusted based on the source material analyzed.

The final preprocessing step is an output normalization. A neural network will be able to learn more consistently and accurately if the outputs occupy the whole range of the associated activation function. Therefore, we calculate the minimum and range of each bin through the set of observations, and normalize each bin as follows:

$$D_{norm} = \frac{D - \min(D)}{\max(D) - \min(D)} \quad (1)$$

This only affects the training of the ANN without affecting the resynthesis, because during synthesis, the outputs will be denormalized as

$$\hat{D} = D_{norm} \cdot (\max(D) - \min(D)) + \min(D) \quad (2)$$

1.2 Offline ANN Training

This metadata file is then used to train the ANN with the C library, FANN, which implements a multilayer feed-forward ANN [3]. For the present work, we have settled on a 4-layer network (input layer, 2 hidden layers, and output layer). Depending on the truncation of the BFCCs/Bark spectrum, the input layer possesses 6, 8, or 23 neurons, corresponding to the number of coefficients, plus pitch, inharmonicity, and loudness. The output layer will have 40 neurons, corresponding with the number of harmonics we represent.

The optimal number of neurons for the two hidden layers is not yet known, but a general structure of data compression followed by expansion has yielded good results.

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We have experimented with many arrangements of neurons for hidden layers, but the specific number of neurons chosen seems to be of little consequence.

At present, this work makes use of only the sigmoid activation function for each neuron, despite current consensus that there are superior activation functions such as ReLU and leaky ReLU. This is simply due to the fact that the FANN library does not contain these functions.

1.3 Realtime Sound Synthesis

The WTIANNs sound synthesis itself is fairly straightforward. A voice of the synthesizer is responsible for producing a periodic phasor at the desired f_0 , and for calculating waveforms any time the performer requests a new timbre. These requests happen any time the control parameters change. The control parameters correspond with the inputs of the neural network: pitch, inharmonicity, loudness, and BFCCs/Barks.

The phasor is used to simultaneously read from two lookup tables containing wavetables. Over the course of an audio block, a linear crossfade is performed to transition from one wavetable to another.

New waveforms are calculated as follows. When the user requests a new timbre, this list is sent as an input to the ANN, which computes an associated set of outputs (bin amplitudes). These outputs are raised to the power of $3.\overline{33}$, to reverse the prior spectral shaping in preprocessing (the power of 0.3). Then, the outputs are denormalized as in equation (2). These outputs are copied into a frequency lookup table, starting from the first index after DC. This frequency table should have a total length that is a power of 2 so that it can be transformed using an FFT. One more step is necessary before the FFT: the current spectrum must be reflected around the Nyquist component in order to represent the negative frequencies. There is no need to take a complex conjugate because phase has been discarded. Next, the FFT is taken from the frequency table. This renders a time domain single-cycle waveform, which is interpolated with cubic interpolation.

In the future, we hope to explore the use of Keras instead of FANN and test if better accuracy can be attained with non-sigmoidal activation functions. We also hope to test more psychoacoustic parameters. Finally, we would like to expand our method to include non-harmonic components, and use synthesis methods other than wavetable.

2. REFERENCES

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